

**ON A SET OF FIXED POINTS RELATED TO BOTH FERMAT
AND MERSENNE PRIMES**

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Abstract

Motivated by a sequence of polynomials from Hodge Theory, we define an arithmetical function $f(n)$ and we prove that its fixed points are related to both Fermat and Mersenne primes.

1. Introduction

For any integer $n \geq 1$, consider the polynomial

$$E(X^{[n]}; q) := (q^n - q^{n-1}) \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 1 \pmod{2}}} (q^{\gamma_n(d)} - q^{1-\gamma_n(d)}), \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma_n(d) := \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2n}{d} - d + 1 \right)$. From a Hodge-theoretic point of view [4], $E(X^{[n]}; q)$ is E-polynomial of the Hilbert scheme $X^{[n]}$ of n points on the algebraic torus $X := \mathbb{C}^\times \times \mathbb{C}^\times$. The quotient $E(X^{[n]}; q)/(q-1)^2$ is a polynomial whose coefficients are nonnegative integer, named *Kassel-Reutenauer q -analog of the sum of divisors* [2].

Several number-theoretic properties of these polynomials were studied in the author's Master Memoir [1]. Also, the coefficients of $E(X^{[n]}; q)$ are related to well-matched parentheses [3].

If q is a prime power [5, 6] then $E(X^{[n]}; q)$ is the number of ideals I of the algebra $\mathbb{F}_q[x, y, x^{-1}, y^{-1}]$ such that the quotient $\mathbb{F}_q[x, y, x^{-1}, y^{-1}]/I$, viewed as a vector space over \mathbb{F}_q , has dimension n . Furthermore, the sequence $(C_n(q))_{n \geq 1}$ evaluated at some roots of unity [7] can be expressed as the Fourier coefficient of certain η -products.

It follows from (1) that

$$E(X^{[n]}; q) = q^{2n} - q^{2n-1} - (-1)^{\kappa(n)} q^{f(n)+1} + R_n(q),$$

for some polynomial $R_n(q)$ whose degree is at most $f(n)$, where $\kappa(n)$ and $f(n)$ are the arithmetical functions defined below.

For each integer $n \geq 1$, define the arithmetical function

$$\kappa(n) := \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n = 2^k \text{ for some } k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}; \\ \min M_n, & \text{otherwise;} \end{cases}$$

where $M_n := \{d, \frac{2n}{d} : d|n, d > 1 \text{ and } d \equiv 1 \pmod{2}\}$. Let $f(n)$ be the arithmetical function given by

- (i) $f(2^k) := 0$ for all $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$;
- (ii) $\frac{n}{\kappa(n)} - \frac{f(n)}{\kappa(n)+1} = \frac{1}{2}$, for all $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, provided that $n \neq 2^k$ for all $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$.

The values of $\kappa(n)$ and $f(n)$, for $1 \leq n \leq 25$, are given in the following table.

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
$\kappa(n)$	0	0	2	0	2	3	2	0	2	4	2	3	2	4	2
$f(n)$	0	0	3	0	6	6	9	0	12	10	15	14	18	15	21

The first polynomials $E(X^{[n]}; q)$ are

$$\begin{aligned} E(X^{[1]}; q) &= q^2 - 2q + 1, \\ E(X^{[2]}; q) &= q^4 - q^3 - q + 1, \\ E(X^{[3]}; q) &= q^6 - q^5 - q^4 + 2q^3 - q^2 - q + 1, \\ E(X^{[4]}; q) &= q^8 - q^7 - q + 1, \\ E(X^{[5]}; q) &= q^{10} - q^9 - q^7 + q^6 + q^4 - q^3 - q + 1, \\ E(X^{[6]}; q) &= q^{12} - q^{11} + q^7 - 2q^6 + q^5 - q + 1, \\ E(X^{[7]}; q) &= q^{14} - q^{13} - q^{10} + q^9 + q^5 - q^4 - q + 1, \\ E(X^{[8]}; q) &= q^{16} - q^{15} - q + 1, \\ E(X^{[9]}; q) &= q^{18} - q^{17} - q^{13} + q^{12} + q^{11} - q^{10} - q^8 + q^7 + q^6 - q^5 - q + 1. \end{aligned}$$

We recall that a prime number $p = 2^m + 1$, with $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, is called *Fermat prime*. Similarly, a prime number $p = 2^m - 1$, with $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$, is called *Mersenne prime*. Furthermore, n is a *fixed point* of f if $f(n) = n$. The goal of this paper is to prove the following elementary result.

Theorem 1. *The function $f(n)$ has infinitely many fixed points if and only if at least one of the following statements holds:*

- (i) *there are infinitely many Fermat primes;*
- (ii) *there are infinitely many Mersenne primes.*

2. Proof of the Main Result

We proceed to prove the main result of this paper.

Proof of Theorem 1. Notice that, by definition of f , an integer $n \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$ is a fixed point of f if and only if

$$\kappa(n) (\kappa(n) + 1) = 2n. \tag{2}$$

Suppose that $n = \frac{p(p+1)}{2}$, where $p = 2^m - 1$ is a Mersenne prime and $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Then $\kappa(n) = p < p + 1 = 2^m = \frac{2n}{p}$. The left hand side of (2) becomes $\kappa(n) (\kappa(n) + 1) = p (p + 1)$, which coincides with its right hand side $2n = p (p + 1)$. Hence, n is a fixed point of f .

Suppose that $n = \frac{(p-1)p}{2}$, where $p = 2^m + 1$ is a Fermat prime and $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Then $\kappa(n) = 2^m = \frac{2n}{p} = p - 1 < p$. The left hand side of (2) becomes $\kappa(n) (\kappa(n) + 1) = (p - 1)p$, which coincides with its right hand side $2n = (p - 1)p$. Hence, n is a fixed point of f .

Now, suppose that n is a fixed point of f . The equation (2) implies that $\kappa(n) \neq 0$. So, $n \neq 2^k$ for all $k \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0}$, i.e. n has an odd divisor greater than 1.

Suppose that $\kappa(n)$ is an odd prime number. Let d be the largest odd divisor of $\kappa(n) + 1$. Notice that $2d$ divides $\kappa(n) + 1$. The obvious inequality $2d \leq \kappa(n) + 1$ implies that $d \leq \frac{\kappa(n)+1}{2} < \kappa(n)$. In virtue of the extremal property of μ , we conclude that $d = 1$, i.e. $\kappa(n) + 1 = 2^m$, for some $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Hence, $n = \frac{(p-1)p}{2}$, where p is a Mersenne prime.

Suppose that $\kappa(n)$ is not an odd prime number. By definition of κ we have $\kappa(n) = 2^m$, for some $m \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 1}$. Let d be the largest divisor of $\kappa(n) + 1$ satisfying $d < \kappa(n) + 1$. So, $d < \kappa(n)$, because d is odd and $\kappa(n)$ even. In virtue of the extremal property of μ , we conclude that $d = 1$, i.e. $\kappa(n) + 1$ is prime. Hence, $n = \frac{p(p+1)}{2}$, where p is a Fermat prime.

We have shown that there is a bijection between the set fixed points of $f(n)$ and the set of both Fermat and Mersenne primes. Therefore, there are infinitely many fixed points of $f(n)$ if and only if the set of both Fermat and Mersenne primes is infinite. □

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